

ABSTRACT

It is believed that a person's formative years in school are the most important time in their development. During these years, students will learn extremely basic yet essential macro skills like reading, writing, listening, and speaking. As students grow and move from secondary to higher education, these many talents will become more refined and are vital. Lacking this fluency, students generally struggle to comprehend more difficult concepts in their career. Even before the pandemic, this was a problem. Due to the pandemic, the students must stay at home and complete their homework without much guidance from their teachers, allowing their parents to handle the more challenging tasks. Many parents find it difficult to teach their kids at home since they don't have the time or patience, especially in the early years. Many parents expressed their annoyance and helplessness on social media. The secretary of the Department of Education, Leonor Magtolis Briones, however, reminds them that parents have a crucial role in their children's success, not only in the lessons they learn from their teachers but also in the supervision to promote whole-person development. But once more, can parental involvement aid in students' literacy development? This study aims to discuss the importance of parental involvement in the literacy development of students. The researcher believes that students will learn more if it is learning from school will be follow-up at home. There would be a consistency in learning especially for the young learners. Eight teachers in the basic education department are interviewed. Their thoughts and ideas are carefully analyzed, it was strongly believed that parental involvement is indeed an important factor in the literacy development of students.

Keywords: *Parent involvement, literacy development, education, teacher*

INTRODUCTION

It is believed that a person's formative years in school are the most important time in their development. During these years, students will learn extremely basic yet essential macro skills like reading, writing, listening, and speaking. As students grow and move from secondary to higher education, these many talents will become more refined and are vital. Lacking this fluency, students generally struggle to comprehend more difficult concepts in their career. Even before the pandemic, this was a problem. Due to the pandemic, the students must stay at home and complete their homework without much guidance from their teachers, allowing their parents to handle the more challenging tasks. Many parents find it difficult to teach their kids at home since they don't have the time or patience, especially in the early years. Many parents expressed their annoyance and helplessness on social media. The secretary of the Department of Education, Leonor Magtolis Briones, however, reminds them that parents have a crucial role in their children's success, not only in the lessons they learn from their teachers but also in the supervision to promote whole-person development. But once more, can parental involvement aid in students' literacy development? This study aims to discuss the importance of parental involvement in the literacy development of students. The researcher believes that students will learn more if it learning from school will be follow-up at home. There would be a consistency in learning especially for the young learners.

Family literacy, according to Saracho (2017), refers to parents and their kids using literacy collectively at home. In the course of their daily activities, they naturally engage in literacy activities. Studies on parental literacy demonstrate how it affects children's literacy growth. Family literacy studies have shown for more than 50 years how crucial it is for parents to support their children's literacy development. On the basis of family literacy research, language and literacy theories have been developed. There is proof that family literacy programs help children develop their literacy. To determine how parental literacy influences early children's literacy development, studies were reviewed. They demonstrated how a range of family-friendly tactics for working with families are necessary for the children's literacy development.

It is commonly recognized that parental participation helps children develop their literacy skills as well as their overall academic success. Particularly important for assisting kids who read below grade level is home literacy. Additionally, research has shown that parent-child interaction quality is just as crucial as interactive opportunities. The study's major goal was to train the participating parents to become literacy coaches for their kids in order to improve read-aloud experiences and improve their ability to assist their kids with reading. Parents and children's interactions supported the findings' highly positive conclusions. The researchers' strategy education and

the interaction with other participating parents, according to the parents who took part, gave them additional skills to be efficient literacy coaches. Findings also demonstrated how challenging it is to encourage family literacy activities among busy parents, particularly those who do not think that reading aloud to their kids can help them become better readers. Brown et al. (2019)

School principals, contending with competing characterizations of parents in education policy and society, may view parents in a number of ways. Two common understandings portray parents as authentic partners or, in contrast, simply supporters of the school's agenda. This paper explores these characterizations by considering the possible link between principals' understandings of parents and their approaches to parent engagement and/or shared decision making, especially in light of the ways that the social context and education policy construct parents of color and working class parents as deficient. We use the lens of social construction of target populations to add to the currently minimal literature that directly examines principals' views of parents. We report findings of a multi-phase analysis of surveys of 667 elementary principals in the state of California and interviews with a subgroup of 34 of these principals. We explore how principals structured parent engagement and conceived of the goals and rationales for parent workshops, illustrating how they socially constructed the target population of parents, particularly parents of color and working class parents. We find that principals often constructed parents in terms of deficiencies and as needing to learn to better support school goals. Our findings have profound implications for advancing equity in schools. Bertrand (2018)

A review of the literature on the impact of family literacy programs on young children's language and literacy development was conducted by Anderson (2017). We define family literacy and then give a brief review of family literacy programs' historical development. The effectiveness of these programs in assisting young children with language and literacy acquisition is also discussed, as well as their predisposition to favor the dominant language (such as English) while ignoring the benefits of bilingualism and families' continued use of their original tongue. Studies on bilingual family literacy programs demonstrate its efficacy in both encouraging the maintenance of the home language and considerably increasing children's early literacy knowledge in the dominant or mainstream language. Meta-analyses show that family literacy programs have a positive impact on young children's language and learning development. The concept of additive bilingualism and bilingual family literacy initiatives are both supported empirically by this finding. We offer some recommendations for future study and practice as our conclusion.

A 2017 study by Kraft et al. found that due to the vast differences in children's summer learning activities, it is highly challenging to provide equal educational opportunities for children in the United States. Center- or school-based interventions are the most common kind used to prevent summer learning loss. In this study, the prospect of enabling parents to provide literacy development opportunities at home as a low-cost option is addressed. The researcher examined a prototype summer text-messaging program for parents that enhanced literacy skills among first through fourth graders in a randomized field study. We discover that third and fourth grade kids have positive effects on their reading comprehension, but first and second grade students do not, with impact sizes ranging from .21 to .29 standard deviations. Texts also increased parent-teacher conferences attendance, but not that of other school-related events. Parents' replies to a follow-up survey give data to guide future attempts to prevent summer learning loss.

The relationship between parental literacy activities with the child, socioeconomic position (SES), and reading literacy was explored by Hemmereichs et al. (2017). To investigate this connection, the researchers use the Bourdieusian theory of habitus development. Early parental involvement in literacy activities (before primary school) and an increasing level of reading literacy and parental education are positively correlated with each other, according to multilevel analyses of a survey of 43,870 students (with an average age of 10 years) in 10 Western European regions. Additionally, it is discovered that kids from lower SES backgrounds experience more late parental involvement in literacy activities (after the fourth year of formal schooling) than kids from higher SES backgrounds.

With 75 articles published between 2003 and 2017, a review that examines the research literature on the connection between parental participation and adolescents' academic attainment. The findings are initially presented in terms of how specific parental participation characteristics, as categorized by age, relate to academic attainment. After that, we do a more thorough literature analysis to identify the factors that are mediating or moderating the link between parental participation and academic accomplishment. Finally, we discuss the developments brought about by research from the previous ten years, paying particular attention to the construct of parental participation.

Educational policies have increasingly promoted parental involvement as a mechanism for improving student outcomes. Few jurisdictions have provided funding for this priority. In Ontario, Canada, the province's Parents Reaching Out Grants program allows parents to apply for funding for a parental involvement initiative that addresses a local barrier to parent participation. This study

categorizes initiatives (N = 11,171) amounting to approximately 10 million dollars (Can\$) in funding from 2009 to 2014 and compares them across school settings. Although results show several key contextual differences, parents across settings identify relatively similar needs for enabling parental involvement, emphasizing parenting approaches for supporting well-being (e.g., nutrition, mental health, and technology use) and skills for home-based learning. However, Epstein's widely used parental involvement typology conceals these prominent aspects of parental involvement. A modified model of parental involvement is presented that may serve as a guide for enhancing parent participation. Hamlin (2016)

The relationship between parents' and teachers' opinions and attitudes toward various forms of parental participation in children's first two years of primary school was discussed in this study. 196 families participated in their child's first year of school, and 124 families continued to participate in their child's second school year. Parents of children in their first year of primary school (age 5) were recruited from 12 classrooms within four schools in New Zealand. The Family-Involvement Questionnaire was filled out by parents in New Zealand, and we archived parent-recorded assignments for oral reading by kids. Teachers' rated helpfulness of parents' involvement at school (level 2) and parents' rated teacher invitations to be involved and their perceived time and energy (level 1) contributed to school-based involvement in Year 1 in multilevel models, with parents' rated teacher invitations for involvement also found to predict Year 1 home-school communication in regression analyses. Contributors to Year 1 child-parent reading in multilevel models included level 1 predictors of two or more adults in the home and parents' perceived time and energy. Longitudinal analyses suggested both consistency and change in each form of involvement from Year 1 to Year 2, with increases in each form of involvement found to be associated with increases in parents' and/or teachers' views about involvement in Year 2 in cross-sectional time-series analyses. Implications for schools wanting to engage families are that parents' involvement in children's schooling may be influenced by parents' perceptions of their capacity, teachers' engagement efforts, and the school's climate for involvement. This is a special issue paper "Family Engagement in Education and Intervention". McDowall et al (2017)

This quantitative synthesis of 448 independent studies including 480,830 families revealed small positive associations ($r_s = .13$ to $.23$) between parents' naturally occurring involvement in children's schooling and children's academic adjustment (i.e., achievement, engagement, and motivation) that were maintained over time. Parents' involvement was also positively related to children's social ($r = .12$) and emotional adjustment ($r = .17$) and negatively related to their delinquency ($r = -.15$), concurrently. Analyses focusing on children's academic adjustment revealed that different types of involvement (e.g., parents' participation in school events and discussion of school with children) were similarly positively associated with such adjustment. The only exception was that parents' homework assistance was negatively associated with children's achievement ($r = -.15$), but not engagement ($r = .07$) or motivation ($r = .05$). There was little variation due to age, ethnicity, or socioeconomic status in the links between different types of involvement and children's academic adjustment. Barger, et al (2019).

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This research essentially made use a qualitative descriptive research design to understand profoundly the teacher perceptions of the informants regarding the parental involvement in the education of students. Lambert (2012) cited Sandelowski, who stated that qualitative descriptive research should be viewed as a categorical, as opposed to a non-categorical, alternative for inquiry; is less interpretive than a "interpretive description" approach because it does not require the researcher to move as far from or into the data; and, in comparison to other qualitative designs, does not require a conceptual or highly abstract rendering of the data. It aimed to highlight the views of Basic Education teachers regarding the importance of the parent's involvement in the development of students especially academically. The findings of the study if proven positive shall be given to the school head and this will be coordinated to the student's parent. This will help the school involve parents in the education of their children.

Participants. This study derived information using convenience sampling from the Basic Education Teacher of a school in Bulacan. Eight teachers have been teaching in this school.

The following is the list of criteria met by the candidates:

1. Has been teaching for more than three (3) years.
2. Currently teaching in the Basic Education Department.

Data Collection Procedure. To conduct the study, the researcher sought approval from both the participants and the administrators of the school. The researcher organized a Zoom interview with the participants after obtaining the permit in order to observe safety procedures due to the ongoing epidemic. Before the interview started, the researcher first described the study's purpose. Additionally, the participant's consent was sought by the researcher before the interview was recorded. The researcher used an interview guide to capture the needed data for this study. The interview guide consisted of questions focused on the perceptions of teachers on the parental involvement.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Parents roles in Students' Education

Parents as First teachers of Students

Children's parents are regarded as their first teachers. They are the ones who begin by teaching their child the fundamentals. The child's literacy may be supported by simple ma-ma, da-di, pa-pa, lo-lo, etc. They have the most influence on what information the child will have access to because they are the ones that engage with the child the most frequently and as a result, they have the most responsibility for how the child develops. They were the first to introduce youngsters to literacy, numeracy, and self-help skills. Additionally, parents help their children develop their academic talents to ensure that they continue to do so outside of the classroom. They should impart fundamental knowledge to their kids and encourage lifelong study.

Parents' habit towards learning are adapted by their children.

Since parents are typically their children's first teachers and they pass on whatever learning habits they instilled in them, parents play a crucial role in their literacy development. Taking reading as an example. In order to acquaint their child with the letter and the words themselves, parents' roles include reading aloud to their children and pointing out words as they do so.

How teachers involve students' parents in literacy development

Take-home activities

Even though students dislike assignments, teachers have utilized them in the past to involve parents in their children's reading development. The parents are asked to assist their children in completing take-home assignments from the teachers, such as reading worksheets and drills. Parents become involved by merely assigning homework to their children because they can explain anything that they don't grasp. A simple assignment, such as talking about their day and the activities they engaged in throughout the day at home, can be assigned that will aid in the learner's development and meet their needs. The teacher may involve the parents of the students by simply asking them to guide their children regarding their home works, reading them stories, or engaging the child in activities that are related to reading and writing. Watching phonemics awareness videos may help as well.

Teachers involve parent in the learning progress of their children

The teacher update the parents on their children's academic achievement. So they can contribute if there is a need for parental help at home. The support of the parents is still crucial even when the progress is good. Describe their child's literacy level. Give them instructions on what to do and how to carry out the instructions in an efficient manner. By providing them homework, they involve their parents in their education and help them grow their literacy while also developing their interpersonal skills.

Effect of Parental Involvement in the Literacy Development

Continuity and Consistency of the Student's Learning Skills

It encourages students to continue studying, especially outside of the classroom. The students are also taught that learning continues even while they are not in class. One of the most crucial things is having someone to lead them. Since they are the people with whom they feel the most at ease and who will also aid in the development of social skills and other aspects of learning, their parents should be there such as reading, singing, writing, and other activities.

The involvement of the parents aids the teachers in understanding and tracking the areas of literacy development where each student excels and struggles. The constancy of what the pupils learn is also impacted by parental engagement. Its impact might be seen in the students' final products.

Their participation has a significant impact on their child's literacy. The consistency and continuity of the child's educational lessons might pave the way for mastery. Because they spend more time with their kids than anybody else, parents have a big influence on how well their kids learn to read. As a result, they have more chances to implement what their child learns in class outside of the classroom. For instance, reading the signage while driving or inside a shopping. They have the greatest impact and influence on the child because they are their primary educators, which helps with the child's general development and literacy growth. In addition to that the involvement of parents in the literacy development of their child is important because they see them as their role models who they can copy and follow.

Summary of Ideas

The parental involvement of students is positively viewed by teachers in the school. Contrary to some beliefs, it is revealed that parents have the most influence on what information the child will have access to because they are the ones that engage with the child the most frequently and as a result, they have the most responsibility for how the child develops. Since they are the first teachers, parents' habit towards learning are adapted by their children. This is why teachers are involving student's parent in the learning process. The Parent Teacher Conference (PTC) is very important. This is where teachers discussed the developments of the students. Parents can be more active in teaching their kids at home. This will complete the process of learning. The things that they learned from school will be continued since students will be given task to accomplished at home. The teacher may involve the parents of the students by simply asking them to guide their children regarding their home works, reading them stories, or engaging the child in activities that are related to reading and writing. Watching phonemics awareness videos may help as well. The constancy of what the pupils learn is also impacted by parental engagement. Its impact might be seen in the students' final products.

CONCLUSION

The parents involvement is very important in the literacy development of students. It can help the students to be more active in class. In addition to that it is beneficial not only to the literacy development but also in the other aspects of life of students. Parental involvement inspires children to learn, which results in improved grades. The degree of participation is essential in creating a significant impact on the student's performance. The parent's level of involvement has a greater influence on the child's academic performance. A more thorough parent-teacher orientation for each class is what the researcher recommends as a suggestion as opposed to gathering all parents for a single orientation. It must be done concurrently by teachers in each classroom. Parents must be shown student work, and take-home assignments must involve parents in addition to being completed at home.

REFERENCES

- Barger, M. M., Kim, E. M., Kuncel, N. R., & Pomerantz, E. M. (2019). The relation between parents' involvement in children's schooling and children's adjustment: A meta-analysis. *Psychological Bulletin*, 145(9), 855–890. <https://doi.org/10.1037/bul0000201>
- Brown, Clara Lee; Schell, Robin; Denton, Rachel; Knode, Elizabeth *School Community Journal*, v29 n1 p63-86 2019 <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1219795>
- Bertrand, Melanie; Freelon, Rhoda; Rogers, John *Education Policy Analysis Archives*, v26 n102 Aug 2018 <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1189589>
- Daniel Hamlin, Joseph Flessa *Parental Involvement Initiatives: An Analysis* First Published October 19, 2016 Research Article <https://doi.org/10.1177/0895904816673739>
- Jim Anderson, Ann Anderson & Assadullah Sadiq (2017) Family literacy programmes and young children's language and literacy development: paying attention to families' home language, *Early Child Development and Care*, 187:3-4, 644-654, DOI: 10.1080/03004430.2016.1211119

- Fan, X., Chen, M. Parental Involvement and Students' Academic Achievement: A Meta-Analysis. *Educational Psychology Review* 13, 1–22 (2001).
<https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1009048817385>
Olivia N. Saracho (2017) Literacy in the twenty-first century: children, families and policy, *Early Child Development and Care*, 187:3-4, 630-643, DOI: 10.1080/03004430.2016.1261513
- Matthew A. Kraft, Manuel Monti-Nussbaum First Published October 25, 2017 Research Article
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0002716217732009>
- Kenneth Hemmereichs, Orhan Agirdag & Dimokritos Kavadias (2017) The relationship between parental literacy involvement, socio-economic status and reading literacy, *Educational Review*, 69:1, 85-101, DOI: [10.1080/00131911.2016.1164667](https://doi.org/10.1080/00131911.2016.1164667)
- Maureen, I.Y., van der Meij, H. & de Jong, T. Supporting Literacy and Digital Literacy Development in Early Childhood Education Using Storytelling Activities. *IJEC* 50, 371–389 (2018).
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13158-018-0230-z>
- Martin, A., Marsh, H., McInerney, D., Green, J., & Dowson, M. (2007). Getting Along with Teachers and Parents: The Yields of Good Relationships for Students' Achievement Motivation and Self-Esteem. *Australian Journal of Guidance and Counselling*, 17(2), 109-125.
doi:10.1375/ajgc.17.2.109
- Lisa Boonk, Hieronymus J.M. Gijsselaers, Henk Ritzen, Saskia Brand-Gruwel, A review of the relationship between parental involvement indicators and academic achievement, *Educational Research Review*, Volume 24, 2018, Pages 10-30, ISSN 1747-938X,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2018.02.001>.
(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1747938X18301027>)
- Philippa S. McDowall, Mele Taumoepeau, Elizabeth Schaughency, Parent involvement in beginning primary school: Correlates and changes in involvement across the first two years of school in a New Zealand sample, *Journal of School Psychology*, Volume 62, 2017, Pages 11-31, ISSN 0022-4405, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsp.2017.03.001>.

Declaration of Conflicting Interest. There are no conflicts concerning this research paper, authorship, and publication.

Funding. No funding from external sources, such as donations or grants, was received for conducting research, authorship, and publication of this paper.